

Socially Responsible Human Resource Management and Turnover Intention Relations: Does Employer Brand Matter?

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Abstract

Since high employee turnover rates have emerged as one of the main problems in the tourism sector, the aim of this paper is to examine the relationship between socially responsible human resource management (SR-HRM), employer brand and employee turnover intention. The paper also aims to investigate whether employees' employer brand perceptions moderate the relationship between SR-HRM and turnover intentions. An empirical study is conducted on hospitality sector. Quantitative research method is used by collecting questionnaires from 209 employees working in five-star hotels in Turkey. Based on the structural equation modelling the results of the study indicated that SR-HRM practices influenced employees' turnover intentions. Furthermore, interpreted organizational identity image (IOII), which is considered a sub-dimension of employer brand in the study, has a moderate effect on the relationship between the SR-HRM perceptions of employees and their turnover intentions. Major contribution of this research is that there is limited amount of research is available attempting to measure employer brand perceptions and considering the employer brand as moderating variable in the SR-HRM practices and employees' turnover intention link as well.

Key words: Socially Responsible Human Resource Management, Turnover Intention, Employer Brand, Human Resource Management

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1. Introduction

As long discussed in the service literature, developing and protecting qualified human resources is a way of providing a competitive advantage in hospitality operations (Albrecht et al., 2015; Evans, 2016). Nonetheless, regarding

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employee protection and some of the articles, highlights the role of various models in preventing employee turnover (Haque, 2021; Holtom et al., 2005; Mobley, 1977). The turnover intention, which is a result of turnover behavior (Tett & Meyer, 1993), is considered together with concepts like unemployment and the structure of the labour force at the macro level (Houkes et al., 2003) and associated with individual and group level job performance, organizational citizenship, and other positive and negative attitudes and behaviors towards the organization at the micro level (Huselid, 1995; Wright et al., 2003).

Several studies reveal that human resources management (HRM) practices can be discussed in terms of their effects at both individual and organizational levels, e.g. turnover intention can be a consequence of HRM practices as well as antecedents' turnover behavior (Cohen et al., 2016; Shaw et al., 1998; Tuzun & Kalemci, 2012). In the frame of the tourism industry in Turkey, a high employee turnover rate is one of the distinctive features of the hospitality industry, as the TUYUP (Increasing the Adaptability of Employers and Employees in the Tourism Sector) project found in 2016. According to TUYUP's labor force survey findings, workforce mobility is at 90.9%. Within the reasons for workforce mobility, employees receiving another job offer was one of the most common reasons (58.7%). However, low wages (57.9%) and frequent job changes (54.5%) have become the norm for the tourism sector employees in Turkey.

The integration of the concept of corporate social responsibility with HRM needs to be discussed well for creating a more effective model for turnover management. After 2000, the concept of SR-HRM practices emerged and that they involve a broader scope over and above the legal obligations between the employee and the organization (Morgeson et al., 2013; Porter & Kramer, 2002; Voegtlin & Greenwood, 2016). According to this new concept, conducting HRM practices in a socially responsible way will also contribute to better corporate social responsibility performance (Swanson & Orlitzky, 2006). Within this context, it is thought that SR-HRM practices, which can be used as a tool to ensure good HRM practices and the protection of employees (especially in the hotel industry in Turkey, where the turnover rate is high), will play a role in terms of both individual and organizational outcomes.

By contrast, in recent years, a new perspective has emerged that integrates marketing and HRM research and focuses mainly on the concept of branding in HRM (Amber and Barrow, 1986; Russell & Brannan, 2016; Timming, 2017). The concept of employer branding has started to be used today as a tool for businesses to distinguish themselves from their competitors. (Ambler & Barrow, 1996; Backhaus & Tikoo, 2004; Dabirian et al., 2017; Edwards, 2010; Gilani & Cunningham, 2017; Lievens et al., 2007; Tanwar & Prasad, 2017). This concept includes the idea that organizational branding makes sense and that employees' perceived reputation of organization plays an important role in HRM, which in turn influences the key HRM processes and results. The concept of employer branding, which is defined as the combined functional, economic and psychological benefits offered by an employer (Ambler & Barrow 1996),

emphasizes that brand marketing principles can be integrated with HRM processes in order to improve basic goal oriented HRM functions such as attracting potential candidates, increasing recruitment efficiency, and increasing the loyalty of existing employees. For example, according to Turban and Greening (1996), the significance placed on socially responsible practices by organizations, i.e., a strong community–employee relationship, environmental policy, product quality and approach to minority groups, within the framework of employer brands, can make these organizations more enticing as potential employers. Furthermore, SR-HRM practices that have an impact on the outward image of the company in shaping the employer brand (Martin et al., 2011), i.e. which aim to create the perception of an organization being “a great place to work for”, have been discussed in terms of the intention to leave at the organization level (Priyadarshi, 2011). The messages conveyed as part of employer branding communication should emphasize the socially responsible aspect of its HRM practices so that the organization can be considered by potential candidates as the "best place to work" (Biswas & Suar, 2014; Kucherov & Zavyalova, 2012; Martin et al., 2011; Turban & Greening, 1996).

In the context of the causality and research, in this study it is thought that the perceived employer brand moderates the negative association between perceived SR-HRM practices and employees' turnover intention.

2. Antecedents of Turnover Intention: SR-HRM and Employer Brand

Turnover intention has been demonstrated to be as the major determinant of the turnover behavior in the organizational behavior literature (Mobley et al., 1978; Newman, 1974; Steel & Ovale, 1984; Tett & Meyer, 1993), and it is normally defined as an employee’s conscious and willing desire to leave an organization within a short period (Tett & Meyer, 1993). Studies in the related literature reveal that there is a negative relationship between high employee turnover and the productivity and profitability of an organization (Brown et al., 2009), employee performance and social capital. The relationship between employee turnover rate and HRM practices can be understood in terms of the effects of those practices on employees' turnover intentions (Tuzun, 2013a). It has been demonstrated that effective HRM practices positively affect companies’ tangible financial indicators, such as productivity, profitability, financial performance, as well as HRM-oriented tangible indicators at the individual level, such as labor turnover rate, absenteeism, and employee attitudes and behaviors (Huselid, 1995; Wright et al., 2003).

Studies on the role of HRM practices in controlling the employee turnover rate have shown that different HRM practices may affect the employees' turnover intentions in different ways (Arthur, 1994; Cohen et al., 2016; Juhdi et al., 2013; Maier et al., 2013). In this context, workforce selection and placement practices designed in accordance with strategic goals will enable the hiring of a workforce

with the required knowledge, skills, and abilities (Combs et al., 2007), and matching the right job with the right candidate will provide the opportunity to manage the possible workforce turnover rate by increasing employee performance and productivity (Arthur, 1994; Wright & Snell, 1998). As well as this, job analysis is an important tool that can affect the employee turnover rate due to its role in providing the outputs required for all the tasks performed in the enterprise and ensuring that the tasks are carried out effectively (Judhi et al., 2013; Maier et al., 2013; Tuzun, 2013a). Some studies have shown that it is possible to evaluate the effect of HRM practices on employee turnover via the job analysis process (Tuzun, 2013a; Tuzun, 2013b). In addition, reductions in employee turnover and absenteeism rates can be observed with the provision of on-the-job and off-the-job training (Chang et al., 2013; Wei, 2015). Studies examining the relationship between performance appraisal and employee turnover emphasize that accessible performance appraisal processes significantly increase employee productivity. HRM training and development practices, which have an important role in increasing employees' productivity, also affect the employee turnover rate (Madera, 2017). In another study, the turnover intention of employees, whose performance was observed to increase with effective training and development practices, also underwent a decrease at the same rate (Truss, 2001).

The high employee turnover rate of the tourism sector is a common problem in Turkey as well as globally. In the hospitality industry, antecedents of turnover intention include poor salaries, long working hours, heavy workload, in-house recruitment, inadequate training and training facilities and limited development opportunities (Madera et al., 2017). Given the increased employee turnover rate in Turkey's hospitality industry, it is necessary to investigate the rationale of employees' intentions to leave from the point of view of HRM practices. Considering the negative impact of voluntary workforce turnover on the economic and social processes of a company, HRM practices have an important role in the control of the employee turnover rate. In the context of theoretical causality and empirical support, it is argued in this study that employees' effective perceptions of HRM practices in terms of social responsibility will adversely affect their turnover intention.

SR-HRM processes represent transparent and objective personnel selection and placement practices (Dupont et al., 2013) together with objective, transparent and non-discriminatory training practices that aim to develop skills (Celma et al., 2014). The early research on social responsibility implementations have been conducted mostly at institutional and corporate levels and focus mostly on external stakeholders (Aguinis & Glavas, 2012). However, discussions on social responsibility and its effect at the micro level can also be found in the relevant literature (Glavas & Kelley, 2014; Shen & Zang, 2019), i.e. the manner by which social responsibility activities at corporate level have a positive influence on employee performance (Sun & Yu, 2005), loyalty (Maignan et al., 1999) and an organization's attractiveness (Greening & Turban, 2000). Moreover, the concept started to gain importance when it began to be discussed alongside HRM (Jamali et al., 2015; Nie et al., 2019; Sarvaiya et al., 2018; Voegtlin & Greenwood, 2016).

As mentioned above the social responsibility of HRM practices, that contribute to improving the quality of work and life of employees (Dupont et al., 2013; Shen & Zhu, 2011) and that ensure HRM practices are maintained in accordance with principles such as objectivity, fairness, transparency, and non-discrimination. SR-HRM practices can be placed into three main categories, namely, labor force-law compliant HRM, employee-oriented HRM and HRM practices that facilitates corporate social responsibility initiatives (Shen & Zhu, 2011; Voegtlin & Greenwood, 2016). Studies show that SR-HRM increases the satisfaction of employees and their allegiance to the organization (Albrecht et al., 2015; Beer et al., 2015; Barrick et al., 2015; Shen & Benson, 2016). Based on these studies, it is possible to say that SR-HRM practices can be utilized to increase the welfare of the employees, as well as indirectly contributing to organizational success in the long term due to the increased satisfaction and loyalty of the employees. Nonetheless, SR-HRM practices allow organizations to increase social welfare by positively affecting society by developing workforce practices according to legitimized social responsibility principles (Paauwe & Farndale, 2017).

In the light of the above explanations, the first hypothesis is:

H1: Perceived SR-HRM practices have a negative relationship with employees' turnover intention.

Because of the importance of attracting qualified employees and keeping existing employees, the concept of employer branding has become an important topic (Dabirian et. al., 2017; Gardner et. al., 2011; Gilani & Cunningham, 2017; Lievens & Highhouse, 2003; Mosley, 2007). Employer branding may be viewed as a long-term strategy for managing existing and future workers' and stakeholders' impressions and views (Sullivan, 2004). In this context, employer branding implementations, such as career development opportunities in the organization (e.g. training and progress opportunities), adequate wages and fair reward systems, positive organizational culture, and enable the development of the human resources at the convenience of the organization. When the concept of employer branding is evaluated in line with the basic assumption of the resource-based approach, the human resources developed through these implementations will enable businesses to gain and maintain a competitive advantage. However, when the concept of employer branding is theoretically associated with all the mutual expectations of employees with the organization (Levinson et al., 1962; Mangold & Miles, 2007), this relationship can be explained by the social change theory (Blau, 1964). The fact that employer branding practices are basically based on mutual relations and obligations between the organization and the employee means they benefit both parties within the framework of reciprocity (Gouldner, 1960).

Current literature indicates that the perceived employer branding of a company has some positive effects on employee job-related attitudes and behavior (Knox & Freeman, 2006; Theurer et al., 2018), whereby employees respond

positively to their organizations in the face of perceived employer brand practices in the context of economic, social and functional benefits (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). The concept claimed as of its functional and/or economic benefits such as physical working conditions, fringe benefits, wages and social issues and psychological benefits such as protecting employees' self-identity, expressing themselves and improving their personal image which offered to the employee by the employer (Ambler & Barrow, 1996). Where an employer's brand and practices are perceived to be good, there is increased employee loyalty and performance levels, ensuring employee continuity and decreasing recruitment costs (Barrow & Mosley, 2005; Berthon et al., 2005; Knox & Freeman, 2006; Theurer et al., 2018). In the process of establishing a strong employer brand, factors such as treating employees equally, providing equality in awards, and creating a positive working environment may affect the intention to leave. In this context, a positive perception of an employer's brand will decrease its employees' turnover intentions.

In the light of the above explanations, the second hypothesis is:

H2: Perceived positive employer brand will have an inverse relationship with employee turnover intention.

3. Moderating Effect of Perceived Employer Brand

Employer brand awareness and image are mostly influenced by outcomes, such as the quality and quantity of potential candidates and applications, rather than current workers inside the business, according to studies that integrate employer branding and HRM effectiveness (Dineen & Williamson, 2012; Tumasjan, 2020). However, there are some studies have investigated the effect of employer brand on existing employees. Through the knowledge and brand awareness provided to the employee and the opportunity for self-development provided by HRM practices and socially responsible initiatives, employee turnover intention can be kept under control. Should SR-HRM practices come to the forefront in organizations, they could become influential on employees' work-related behavior, and having a strong employer brand could strengthen these organizations. Since the concept of employer branding, which is used as a tool to create the perception of a company being "the best place to work for", is based on creating appeal for potential candidates and current employees, it can be assumed that employer brand perception will influence employee retention and therefore strengthen the relationship between SR-HRM practices and turnover intentions.

In the light of the above explanations the third hypothesis is:

H3: Perceived employer brand practices have a moderating effect on the negative relationship between SR-HRM practices and employees' turnover intentions.

4. Methodology

Sample and Data

The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between SR-HRM, employees' perceptions of employer brand practices and their turnover intention, and to investigate the moderated effect between variables. In order to test the hypotheses, a survey was administered among employees in the hospitality industry in Turkey. The research was carried out with the participants working at five-star hotels in Ankara, Turkey. Data were collected from the participants using a questionnaire method. A survey was conducted with 209 forms, after excluding the half-filled questionnaires out of 246 forms that could not be used. In the case of using structural equation modeling, there is a general consensus that the sample size should be 200 (Garver & Mentzer, 1999; Hoe, 2008). In addition, in the mediation effect analysis performed with SEM, the value of 200 in the sample number is accepted as the cutoff value (MacKinnon and Fairchild, 2009; Preacher and Hayes, 2008). In this context, 209 participants constituting the sample of the study were assumed sufficient.

The questionnaire used to collect data consists of two parts. In the first part, there are 5 items to determine the demographic characteristics of the participants such as age, gender, education level, total working time in the institution and their expertise. In the second part of the study, there are expressions that investigate the employees' perception of SR-HRM practices, their employer brand perception and their turnover intention.

The demographic characteristics of the respondents were as follows: 56 percent of respondents were between 26-20 years old, the female/male ratio was 44% female and 51% male, and 80 percent had a university degree. Demographic characteristics of the respondents are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The demographic characteristics of the respondents

Age	Frequency	%	Gender	Frequency	%	Education	Frequency	%
20-25	18	8.6	Female	93	44.5	High school grad	11	5.3
26-30	56	26.8	Male	108	51.7	Some college	167	79.9
31-35	44	21.1				Master/PHD	14	6.7
36-40	33	15.8						
41-45	16	7.7						
46-50	1	0.5						

Source: Authors' calculations

Measurement and Validation

Turnover intention, which is the dependent variable of the study, was measured with 3 items, five-point Likert-type scale of Mobley et al. (1978) was used which is previously validated in several Turkish articles (e.g. Tuzun 2013; Kalemci and Tuzun, 2012). It has three items, and a sample item as follows: 'I think a lot about leaving the organization'.

The scale measuring employees' perceptions of SR-HRM was adopted from Shen and Zhu (2011), and although it was originally a 13-item scale, only ten items were used as the others were considered general HRM items which is previously validated by in several studies (e.g. Gahlawat and Kundu, 2018). Confirmatory factor analysis was carried out for SR-HRM scale. Items 4, 8, and 10 were removed from the scale consisting of 10 items and were collected under a single variable ($\chi^2 / sd = 1.98$, NFI = 0.94, TLI = .94, CFI = 0.96, RMSEA = 0.06).

To evaluate the employees' perception of the employer brand practices, Amber and Barrow (1996), Knox and Freeman (2006) and Backhaus and Tikoo (2004) studies were used. Sampling items are: "The institution where I work is the best place to work in the sector.", "Working in the institution I work for is attractive to new graduates.", "I would like to work in this institution for the continuation of my career."

Both for the SR-HRM and employer brand scales, the validity analysis is run. It was first translated into Turkish and then back to English, ensuring that the integrity of meaning is preserved. The evaluation of all the scales is in the form of a five-point Likert with anchors ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

We followed Schwab's scale development guidelines for developing the employer brand scale (1980). We used a deductive approach to develop a pool of items for the employer brand scale, which were derived from Amber and Barrow (1996), Knox and Freeman (2006), and Backhaus and Tikoo (2004) studies that evaluated the functional, economic, and psychological benefits of employer brand. A total of 58 items were generated during the item creation process. The initial item pool was checked and analyzed by four academics in the field of HRM. The main goal was to improve the items' readability, consistency, and relevance. The total number of objects in the pool was decreased from 58 to 23 as a result of this process. The data were subjected to exploratory factor analyses using principal axis factoring with oblique rotation to analyze the underlying factor structure of the remaining pool of 23 items. Factor loads, factor common variances and explained total variance and reliability coefficients of the items as a result of factor analysis are presented in Table 2. It should be noted that, items that were not loaded properly (7, 15, 17, 19) were excluded from the next analyses. As a result of the analysis, three factors with eigenvalues greater than one is emerged.

These factors are defined as interpreted organizational identity image (IOII), perceived functional benefit (PFB), and perceived psychological benefit (PPB). In naming the sub-dimensions, employer brand is accepted as a tool to create the perception of great place to work, and the perceived image constitutes the main basis in creating this perception (Knox and Freeman, 2006; De Stobbeleir et. al. 2016).

Table 2: Employer Brand Scale Exploratory Factor Analysis Result

No	Factor	Factor Load		Cronbach Alfa
1	Interpreted Organizational Identity Image	.319		.86
2		.298		
3		.298		
4		.187		
5		.305		
6	Perceived Functional Benefit		.465	.72
8			.341	
9			.313	
10			.336	
11			.281	
12	Perceived Psychological Benefit		.200	.92
13			.217	
14			.134	
16			.049	
18			.099	
20			.144	
21			.133	
22			.236	
23			.186	

Source: Authors' calculations

5. RESULTS

The means, standard deviations, Cronbach alphas and inter-correlations of the final version of the scale's measures are provided in Table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics and correlations

Constructs	1	2	3	4	5
1 SR-HRM	-0.81				
Employer Brand					
2 (Interpreted Organizational Identity image)	.52**	-0.86			
Employer Brand					
3 (Perceived Functional Benefit)	.54**	.59**	-0.79		
Employer Brand					
4 (Perceived Psychological Benefit)	.65**	.69**	.67**	-0.92	
5 Turnover Intention	-.36**	-.46**	-.10**	-.49**	-0.73
<i>Mean</i>	3.77	4.13	4.01	3.89	1.67
<i>SD</i>	0.82	0.84	0.87	0.84	1.4

N:209 () Cronbach's Alpha * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ (two-tailed)

Source: Authors' calculations

Correlation table indicated that turnover intention mostly negatively correlated with psychological benefit dimension of employer brand (-.49). Then turnover intention negatively correlated with respectively IOII (-.46), SR-HRM (-.36) and PFB (-.10). For the further analysis of hypotheses hierarchical regression analysis was undertaken. We test both direct and moderated relations between independent and dependent variables.

As Table 4 indicated, according to the results of Model 1 perceived SR-HRM practices negatively related with employees' turnover intention ($\beta = -.181$, $p < .05$) so H1 is supported. Hypothesis 2 proposes that perceived employer brand practices negatively related with employees' turnover intention. Based on the Model 1 dimension of PPB and IOII negatively related to turnover intention respectively as ($\beta = -.42$, $p < .001$) and ($\beta = -.36$, $p < .001$). Results showed that PFB's direct effect on turnover intention is not statistically significant that is why excluded from the further analysis so H2 is partly supported.

At the second model we entered the interaction terms of SR-HRM and PPB, SR-HRM and IOII in to test their impact on turnover intentions. Table 4 indicates the results of hierarchical regression analysis predicting turnover intentions.

Table 4: Regressions predicting turnover intentions

1st	2nd	β	t	p-value
Direct	Moderated			
(Constant)			8.882	.000
SR-HRM		-.181*	-2.337	.028
PFP		.535	6.349	.092
PPB		-.418**	-3.994	.003
IOII		-.361**	-3.799	.007
<i>Adj. R-squared</i>		.401		
<i>F</i>		20.916		
	(Constant)		10.049	.000
	SR-HRM	-.070*	-.829	.017
	SR-HRM.PPB	.129***	1.217	.000
	SR-HRM.IOII	-.069*	-.652	.012
<i>Adj. R-squared</i>		.259		
<i>F</i>		15.551		

Note: Standardized β -coefficients are reported. N=209. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ Dependent Variable: Turnover intentions

Source: Authors' calculations

According to Model II, SR-HRM still has statistically significant impact on employees' turnover intention ($\beta = -.70$, $p < 0.05$). Within the employer brand dimensions, it is seen that IOII moderated the relationship between SR-HRM and turnover intentions. These results provide partial support for H3.

Likewise, the fact that the effectiveness of SR-HRM practices influences their turnover intention is thought to once again emphasize the importance of the IOII dimensions of employer brand as an internal HRM practice in the protection of existing employees.

On the other hand, the fact that only the interpreted organization identity image of the employer brand has a moderated effect on the relationship between SR-HRM and turnover intentions has emerged as a result consistent with the relevant literature. Consistent with research on external perceptions of employer brand can influence organizational absenteeism rates (De Stobbeleir et al. 2018), our findings showed that external interpretations of image have an impact on organizational outcomes.

6. CONCLUSION

This study examines the relationship between SR-HRM, employer brand and employee turnover intention. The findings of this study address SR-HRM

perceptions of employees negatively affect their turnover intentions and how IOII, a sub-dimension of the employer brand, moderates the negative relationship between SR-HRM and turnover intentions.

The most discussed area of employer branding research addresses internal and external brand practices to employee recruitment and retention in organizations. This study is important in terms of evaluating the impact of SR-HRM practices and employer brand perception on the evaluation of employee turnover intention. Results from the study indicate that perceived organizational identity image has a moderate effect on employee turnover intention. The results, though surprising, highlight the importance of improving an organization's external employer brand image. Furthermore, the research findings are compatible with related literature. The perceived image of employers by current employees and potential recruits could lead to organizations becoming the employer of choice (Backhaus, 2016; De Stobbeleir et al., 2018; Maxwell & Knox, 2009; Turban & Greening, 1996). The findings of this study add to the growing body of research that concludes that, when developing their employer brand, the external image of an organization has become more important than their internal image.

In line with previous employer brand research (De Stobbeleir et al., 2018; Theurer et al., 2018), this study can be discussed with social identity theory (Tajfel, 1974), which proposes that individuals identify themselves as being in different social categories. Also, because of the uniqueness of an organization's identity, employee engagement with that organization increases (Ashforth & Mael, 1989; Maxwell & Knox, 2009). Based on this argument, it is thought that when an employee perceives a relevant organization to be socially responsible, they are increasingly inclined to align themselves with it and, for instance, less likely to leave their job. Furthermore, an outsider's interpretation of an organization's practices might shape how an employee perceives their workplace and affect their intentions.

The perception of an organization's image affects the behaviors of its employees; it is thought that image perception is important for an individual's self-identity and is used as a tool to evaluate their participation in an organization. When an employee is part of a high-performing and respected organization, they are inclined to develop self-awareness, and self-esteem (Carmeli et al., 2007; Dutton et al., 1994). As a result, employees continue to be a part of an organization that they believe is well-regarded by outsiders.

Taking the hospitality industry as an example, the moderating effect of IOII on turnover intentions emerges as a remarkable result that should be emphasized by organizations. When the results are evaluated, especially in establishments providing accommodation, it can be argued that an organization's identity image might be used as a means of controlling the rate of employee turnover. In the tourism sector, where the turnover rate is high, the perceived external image of an enterprise affects employee attitudes and behaviors, therefore, the employer brand can be considered as a useful tool, for instance, to

improve employee retention. Likewise, it is expected that the study will fill this gap due to the limited number of studies dealing with such relationships in the relevant literature.

Another area of research that is thought to contribute to relevant literature is the examination of the concept of employer brand and its sub-dimensions. Using exploratory factor analysis, a scale to measure employer brand was employed and when sub-dimension factors were examined these dimensions were named in parallel with the relevant literature. It is thought that more effective criteria and scales in measuring and evaluating employer brand can be developed with the development of the relevant theoretical ground. In addition, how an organizational identity image is interpreted when potential candidates notice it initially is considered to be a research topic for future studies. Our research suggests that, when controlling employee turnover intentions, organizations should take into account external employer image as a part of their employer brand practices. Additionally, organizations should combine their internal public relations and HRM practices to ensure they are perceived as an employer of choice by current and potential employees.

There are several limitations to this study that could be addressed in future research. The study was carried out using 209 service employees that work in the hospitality sector. In terms of evaluating the results of the study, it would be more meaningful to expand the study by examining different moderated variables with a larger sample that has different demographic and social characteristics. In addition, the results could be evaluated in terms of the cultural context in which the sample is located. Furthermore, different results may be obtained in future research if scales that take into account cultural factors are used. Evaluating SR-HRM practices with research that integrates quantitative and qualitative methods is important in terms of contribution to the literature, however, studies that integrate perceptions of both employees and managers with regards to SR-HRM effectiveness may be more successful in evaluating HRM practices.

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